

One Nation Under God: Achieving National Integration Through Interfaith Relations on the University of Abuja Campus

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Abstract

In contemporary Nigeria, university campuses have become veritable centres not only for religious practices but equally for the recruitment of members by sects, cults, and denominations. Our research project was premised on the assumption that for the country to achieve sustainable integration, undergraduates in the nation's university system should be co-opted as advocates and stakeholders in the onerous task of peacebuilding and interfaith harmony. This paper reports on the initial survey carried out early in the year 2022 among university of Abuja undergraduates (Christian and Muslims) in this regard. The paper used the descriptive research method. A carefully designed questionnaire was administered among five hundred and twenty-four (524) undergraduates from the University. Having deployed the Integrated Phenomenological Approach (IPA) to research, the paper found that respondents were all desirous of a peaceful interfaith space not only on their campus but across Nigeria. They opined that the introduction of a curriculum on interfaith dialogue and the formulation of a policy on religious practices in the Nigerian University System (NUS) would go a long way in entrenching peace among adherents of various religions and ultimately in promoting national integration.

Keywords: Nation, God, National Integration, Interfaith Relations, University of Abuja Campus.

Introduction

Despite the dissonance in their views and perspectives on the nation's multiple challenges, Nigerians largely agree that 'religious' conflicts are unarguably the most insidious factors impeding national integration. The trend which first achieved global attention in 1980 with the outbreak of the Maitasine riot¹ witnessed an upscale in 2009 with the emergence of the Boko Haram in northeastern parts of the country.² Incidences of violence witnessed by the country, exacerbated in part by what Daniel and Andrew referred to as the "Unholy Trinity" of religion, ethnicity, and national identity³ have led to an uncountable number of fatalities.⁴ Recent data in this direction show that deaths recorded by the country from the unconscionable acts of violence being perpetrated by the latter group recently increased from 10,515 in 2017 to 10,665 in 2018.⁵ Thus, the nation's exposure to vulnerability continued to rise even as it is unable to benefit from the multiplex of ethnic nationalities and groups that constitute its citizenry; groups that constantly take adversarial postures, one against the other⁶ over "conflicting interests and values."⁷

Ironically too, Nigeria holds perhaps the greatest promise for peaceful interfaith relations in the continent.⁸ It is noteworthy that over the years, concerted efforts have been made at governmental and non-governmental levels to find lasting solutions to the hydra-headed problem of 'religious' conflicts through the promotion of peace and harmony between Christians and Muslims in the country.⁹ In fact, one of the strategies devised by government in this direction was the establishment, in 1999, of the Nigerian Inter-religious Council (NIREC) with the sole purpose of helping government lay a sustainable foundation for peaceful interfaith relations in the country.¹⁰ However, more than two decades thereafter the search for peace and national integration particularly in otherwise neglected areas of the Nigerian socio-cultural, political, and religious space such as the Nigeria University System (NUS) remains urgent.

In other words, whereas Universities across the world furnish unarguably one of the greatest opportunities for diversity in thought, beliefs, culture, social status, and values among others, experience has shown that they equally serve, and quite ironically, as incubators for conflict and promotion of alterity and otherness. However, in institutions where strong policies and structures are in place, diversity provides an ideal lifelong learning opportunity for engaging with the "other" through intercultural and interreligious education.¹⁰ However, a careful contemplation of efforts by government and non-for-profit organizations that target the promotion of peaceful interfaith relations in Nigeria has shown that adequate attention has not been paid to how Christian and Muslim undergraduates on Nigerian university campuses could contribute to the onerous task of achieving interreligious harmony and national integration. This is evidenced in the lack of critical engagement between the followers of the two main religions (Christianity and Islam), the near total absence of interfaith policies and infrastructures on the campuses and the tendency for the undergraduates to become innocent proselytizers of hate speech and perpetrators of violence against the ethno-religious other in the larger society.¹¹

Consequently, a survey was conducted in late 2021 and early 2022 among undergraduates of the University of Abuja as part of a larger research project that was executed in six universities and across the nation's six geo-political zones. The overarching goal was to account for the depth of the students' awareness of, first, the nexus between peaceful interfaith relations and national integration and, second, the drivers and effects of disharmony in religious practices in the NUS on the nation's search for peace and development. This paper, therefore, presents the results of the survey that elicited more than five hundred responses from Christian and Muslim undergraduates of the University. It provides a brief historical geography of interfaith relations in the University as the microcosm of the larger NUS. It proceeds from there to the review of existing literature in the field to validate its theoretical, analytical and methodological preferences. Variables tested in the survey were stratified in such a way that responses provided showed clarity about the perceptions of Nigerian youths of the nexus between peaceful interfaith relations and national integration.

University of Abuja- Mirroring a Nation in Search of Integration

When in 1988 the University of Abuja was established through Decree No. 110 issued by the military government in Nigeria, the nation welcomed its twenty-first ivory tower. Whereas the overarching intention behind the establishment of the university was to increase access to higher education to the mass of Nigerian youths who could not be admitted by the then existing universities due to their low-level capacities and facilities, the University of Abuja was however meant to serve another purpose. It was envisioned to function as the nation's university of 'cohesion' and 'integration' where Nigerian youths, no matter their tribe or religion, would be able to achieve their scholarly ambition. Since its establishment, the University has therefore admitted students from very diverse backgrounds. They mirror the nation's tribal and religious identities; they represent the nation's hopes and fears for the future.¹²

More than three decades ago after its founding, the University of Abuja campus has largely witnessed a peaceful and harmonious relationship between its Christian and Muslim population, staff, and students. According to Samuel Alifa, a staff in the Department of Philosophy and Religions at the University of Abuja, an exception to the trend, was a disagreement that broke out between Muslim and Christian students of the then Department of

Philosophy and Religions in the year 2012, on the issue of festivities which are usually celebrated at the end of every academic session by the National Association of Philosophy and Religions Students (NAPRES). While a group among the students wanted a carnival-like festival that would feature all sorts of activities including dancing, night parties etc, others, of which the majority were Muslims disagreed. The latter argued that the proposed activities constituted an infraction of Islamic law. This led to an attempt by the Muslim students to opt-out of the association and form a new one. The crisis was however quickly nipped in the bud through the intervention of the students' course adviser. According to him, the university of Abuja was established partly to bring adherents of Christianity and Islam on the campus "into close contact and foster an attitude of cooperation and tolerance."¹³ The university would therefore not allow any outbreak of conflict on its campus in order not to imperil its lofty ideal and mandate. The situation is however different in the larger Nigerian society going by existing literatures in the field.

Review of Literature on Interfaith Relations in Nigeria

*Peaceful interfaith relations normatively refer to that situation or condition in which religious groups live together in peace, respect their differences, and resolve their conflicts in peaceful ways.*¹⁴ It refers not to the absence of conflicts between or among religious groups within a given space of human conurbation such as the university campus, but the conscious decision on the part of religious adherents to avoid violence as a tool for resolution of such conflicts and promote *cooperation, togetherness, mutual consultation and acceptance of difference and diversity.*¹⁵

With reference to Nigeria and the NUS in particular, the above remains an ideal yet to be realised. Pieces of evidence abound that show that Nigeria's national stability, political landscape, cultural and social integration are perennially threatened by violent religious extremism and conflicts that derive strength from the country's political, economic and social fissures and disjuncture. There is equally a disturbing nexus between Nigerian youths, especially students and religious conflicts. Some of them are often employed as instruments in generating and escalating religious crises. They have consequently become innocent tools in the hands of socio-religious groups, terrorist cells and various political interests that have been suspected of causing violent conflicts in Nigeria.¹⁶

Further, the roots of the interreligious tensions between Muslims and Christians in Nigeria have been traced to the British colonial period when, in addition to the forceful occupation of Africa and Asia, young Africans and Asians, especially Muslims, were coerced into accepting Christianity in the missionary schools that were opened by the British missions during the period. The "educational Jihad"¹⁷ launched by Muslim organisations thereafter to confront what became known as Christian "educational evangelism" in the country has ironically endured since the country attained its independence from British colonial powers. But this is from a perspective. The other relates to the quest for the full implementation of the Islamic Law, the rise of Islamic fundamentalism, Christian fundamentalism, the emergence of the Muslim Students' Society of Nigeria (MSSN) and the 'Born-Again' Christians all of which operate on the Nigerian university campuses and are usually in constant competition for authority and patronage. These have all accentuated the conflictual relationships between Christians and Muslims within the NUS.¹⁸

According to Obadere, these factors circumscribed the 'religious' crises the NUS witnessed in, for example, Usman Dan Fodio University, Sokoto and University of Ibadan, both in May 1986. It was inscribed into the crisis that broke out at the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, where the decision by a Muslim lady to wear the veil to lectures led to disquiet between the University authorities and the Muslim students' community.¹⁹ The negative influence that religion has on university undergraduates in the country in the contemporary period has become limited to dressing styles, attendance of prayer sessions in the churches and mosques, unwarranted castigation of the beliefs held by others and egregious perpetration of acts of murder in the defence of one's faith, not that of achieving academic excellence.²⁰

Now how do we account for this situation? Incidences of religious crises on the NUS has largely been a product of religious particularism or the notion that one's faith is the only way to salvation to the exclusion of others.²¹ This is abutted by increasing religious activities on the nation's university campuses. These factors, he argued, equally feed on others in the larger Nigerian society where religious affiliation has become a factor for access to opportunities. In other words, Nigeria remains a state where political Islam finds a counterfoil in political Christianity;²² it is that in which the media feed on religious conflicts for pecuniary purposes;²³ it is a site where, according to Prince Bola Ajibola, a former minister of justice and attorney general of the country, seemingly oppositional categories of religion, politics and ethnicity gain strength from corruption, poverty and insecurity. "It is therefore difficult to solve one without considering all other underpinning factors."²⁴

Crass materialism as an excessive quest for or pursuit of material wealth is one of the major root causes of the above degeneration of interreligious relations in the country. Religious leaders in Nigeria are said to be deeply involved in the acquisition of material wealth no matter the source.²⁵ have argued that common allegations that some religious leaders use diabolical and money-making rituals to attract people to their circles may not be far from the truth. They also opined that the prevalence of such practices is worse in Christianity, where 'prosperity gospel' has replaced asceticism to such an extent that many self-inspired and anointed men of God have compromised their ministries for material benefits.

Theoretical Approach

Since the problem of interest to our project relates to how undergraduates in Nigerian universities have "lived" and experienced religious diversity and how the latter could be leveraged upon in promoting national integration, the interpretive phenomenological approach (IPA) in research therefore became our methodology of choice. This is because IPA is concerned with the detailed examination of how individuals make sense of their lived experience.²⁶ Willig further argues that "If we want to move beyond sharing an experience with our participants, and understand their experiences well enough to explain them, we need to be aware of the conditions that gave rise to these experiences in the first place."

IPA consists of three distinct but mutually complimentary methodological ingredients. These include phenomenology, hermeneutics, and idiography. By phenomenology, the question of exactly what it means being human is privileged.²⁷ Equally important in this direction for researchers is to recognise that the interpretation of people's meaning-making activities and their life experiences can only take place in relation to the researcher's perspective at a particular point in time.²⁸ This is what Merleau-Ponty refers as to the 'meeting point'²⁹ between the self and the world. The notion that the perception of the 'other' develops from one's own embodied perspective. In other words, IPA is framed based on the notion that while researchers can observe and experience empathy for participants, the experience of life and the phenomena usually take place in the subjective; rarely can the self-share the other's experience completely.³⁰ In fact, this becomes even more urgent since our engagement with the world is never static but constantly unfolding.

The second major theoretical ingredient of IPA is derived from hermeneutics - theory of interpretation.³¹ The major postulation here is that in order that sense may be made of what is being said or written close interpretation of the text and the perspective of respondents to the phenomena is a categorical imperative. For this to happen, a complex relationship between the interpreter and the interpreted must be established. This led to suggest that one cannot separate the researcher from the object of research. This is because as we engage in the world, the world changes us, something he refers to as a "fusion of horizons between the researcher and the participant" between the researcher and the participant.³¹

Idiography, the third ingredient in IPA, is concerned with the particular; and this operates at two levels i.e., firstly, in the sense of detail, with a thorough and systematic depth of analysis; and secondly, with an understanding of how a particular experiential phenomenon (an event, process or relationship) has been understood from the perspective of particular people, in a particular context.³² To achieve this, IPA privileges the study of small, reasonably homogenous, purposively selected and carefully situated samples, and may often

make very effective use of a single case analysis. A single case is justified in its own right when it describes something intrinsically interesting. It also demonstrates existence, not incidence, potentially pointing to flaws in existing theoretical claims for a population, disconfirming our expectations, or revealing things that were not expected. Single cases can also be drawn together for further analyses, moving from the single case to more broad claims.³³

Methodology

To have insights into the religious atmosphere in Nigerian Universities, an online survey was conducted across six Universities in the six geo-political zones in the country. The respondents- students/participants were asked to provide answers to the questionnaire designed to assess their perceptions on the reasons behind the different religious crises in the country and suggest ways to reduce the incessant conflicts in the country. The responses pulled from each University was coded, and SPSS version 25 version was used to analyse the data. This paper presents findings from the University of Abuja, in northcentral Nigeria.

Background Information

Respondents to the questionnaire comprised undergraduate students who were, as of January to March 2022, pursuing different degrees at the University of Abuja main campus. Among the 524 responses majority as revealed in the Table 1, were dominated by female students 280 (53.4%) while the rest 244 (46.6%) were male students; and most of them range between 20 – 24 years, forming 297 (56.7%) followed by 25 – 29 years and 15 – 19 years which are 99 (18.9%) and 95 (18.1%) respectively. Also, only two religious practitioners were assessed (Islam, 160 (30.5%), and Christianity, 364 (69.5%). This shows that among the popular sampled, Christian students were more active on the social media than their Muslim counterparts.

Table 1: Background Information

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	244	46.6
Female	280	53.4
Religion		
Islam	160	30.5
Christianity	364	69.5
Age		
15-19	95	18.1
20-24	297	56.7
25-29	99	18.9
30-34	20	3.8
35-39	8	1.5
40-44	5	1.0
Total	524	100.0

1. When conflicts become religious

The respondents were asked about their thoughts on when conflict becomes religious in the country, giving a range of options to select from. The result, as shown in Figure 1, revealed that 300 (57.3%) opined that conflicts become religious when incidences of violence among people of different religions lead to deaths and loss of

properties. Also, 224 (42.7%) said that conflicts become religious when it involves people of different religions, whereas 126 (15.10%) held the view that when violence between Muslims and Christians lead to death and loss of properties then it can be designated as religious conflict. Nonetheless, 73 (8.8%) of the respondents opined that conflict becomes religious when it involves people of the same faith. The remaining group numbering 11 (1.10%) represented a wide variety of opinions. For them, conflicts become religious when people become violent because of misinterpretation of religious texts, lack of tolerance of others' beliefs or ideologies and contestations over which religion is superior to the other.

2. Religious Conflicts in Nigeria

The respondents were asked if they have ever witnessed any religious conflicts in Nigeria. The result, as given in Fig 2, shows that 152 (29.0%) of the respondents have experienced it, while 372 (71.0%) of them have not experienced religious conflict in Nigeria. Those who have experienced religious conflict referred to the conflicts that were orchestrated by the Boko Haram insurgents, who sought to impose what they referred to as Islamic state on Nigeria. Some of the respondents also reported the conflicts that occurred in Jos in 2001, 2002, 2009, 2010 and 2015; Kaduna in 1980, 2011 and 2012; then in the cities of Kano, Kebbi, Abuja, and Ilorin. Precisely, some students reported that:

It (the conflict) happened in Jos in 2015 when an oil tanker fell down on the highway and the villagers started to scoop the oil despite the hot weather and the danger that portended. So, travellers along the road tried to stop them to avoid explosion but unfortunately that incident ended up in a bloody religious conflict – Student number 16.

The conflict that I witnessed occurred in Jos in 2001. The trigger was the mutual distrust on the part of Christians and Muslims who considered each other implacable enemies. Neither party felt safe being neighbours to each other – Student number 449.

The religious crises in Jos 2009, led to loss of lives and properties. Families had to relocate to other states because of the crises. It created a religious division in the state. While a section of Plateau state is occupied by Muslims, the other is populated in the main by Christians. – Student number 332. The crises in Jos between 2009 and 2011 which led to loss of lives and properties started as a conflict between the indigenes and the Fulanis/Hausas – Student number 257.

Some other students reported that:

The conflict that they witnessed took place in Kebbi, Kebbi State. We were coming back from church one Thursday evening; we met three Hausa guys, apparently Muslims, who told us that if we come to church tomorrow, we would be killed. But it meant nothing to us because we had witnessed series of threats like that from them before. They even called us infidels in Hausa language. They believed that practicing Christianity makes you an infidel. Later on Friday, after Jumu'at, Christians were attacked and churches in Jega local government of Kebbi state were destroyed – Students 185.

An incident occurred at Gwagwalada in Abuja that led to the death of a man. While Muslims were in the Mosque praying, a Christian tried to start his bike so that he could leave the Mosque area, but unfortunately, the bike did not start on time but when it finally did, it made a hell of noise. This eventually led to a fight. The man was eventually killed as a result of the conflict – Student number 284.

The conflict that I witnessed took place in Kano shortly after President Goodluck Jonathan was elected. A conflict occurred between a group of Hausas who were predominantly Muslims and others that were Christians. It eventually led to a huge loss of properties. My dad's car was burnt, our house was destroyed. Only God saved us – Student number 496

I witnessed a religious conflict in Kano state in 2011 which was sparked by disagreements over the outcome of the presidential election. It later resulted into a religious crisis. Many people lost their lives including my friend – Student number 420.

Other related responses on religious conflicts indicated that there have been religious crises in Nigeria for a while now. In fact, a student reported that:

Religious conflicts in Nigeria dates to 1985, when General Ibrahim Babangida enrolled Nigeria into the Organization of Islamic conference (OIC). This was the move that aggravated religious tension in the country – Student number 362.

3. Availability or otherwise of policies that promote inter-religious dialogue and peaceful co-existence among Muslims and Christians on Campus.

When probed about existence of policies meant to promote interfaith dialogue or peaceful relationship by the government and/or University, different responses were elicited. Whereas 25.0% of the respondents said there were aware of policies to that effect, the majority of respondents 75% of the respondents reported that they are not aware of the existence of such policies particularly on University of Abuja campus. Those who said that there was a policy in place in the university only referred to the existence of organisations and agencies such as the Interfaith Dialogue Forum for Peace (IDFP), the Nigeria Inter-Religious Council (NIREC), and the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme. Some of the responses are presented below.

Interfaith dialogue, refers to cooperative and positive interactions between people of different religious traditions; it promotes interaction and acceptance of others- examples of such interactions can be found in schools, market, offices, companies etc. – Student number 294.

The Nigeria Inter-Religious Council (NIREC) is working to diffuse tensions between Christians and Muslims here. It has been providing a forum since 1999 to enhance dialogue between Christians and Muslims groups. To a great extent, these dialogues have been working for us. Christians and Muslims are realising that we were all created by one God and that the only way to live is to love one another – Student number 170.

We have the Christian Students Fellowship on Campus, an organization which promote peace amongst both Christian and Muslim students. We also have The Muslim Students' Society of Nigeria (MSSN) on campus that equally preach peace and tranquillity among students – Student number 84.

Seminars and conferences have been organized on campus to foster understanding of the need for peace and inculcate conflict prevention skills among students on the University campus. Many organisations such as UNESCO have organized sensitization programmes on the study of wars and conflict resolution ... for all students on campus – Student number 65.

In my school (University of Abuja) there is an annual program that used to hold here, tagged “UniAbuja Carnival”. The Carnival is meant to promote inter-religious as well as inter-ethnic relationships among people (students) of diverse ethnic and religious beliefs – Student number 489.

4. Cases of religious crises on campus

When asked about cases of religious crises in the respondents' university, result in Fig 4, shows that 8.0% of the respondents have experienced it while 92.0% have not experienced even one instance of religious crisis in the university. Those who claimed to have witnessed crises further reported that the crisis happened in 2019 during the students' union election. According to them, there was an attempt by a Christian group to elect their members to the faculty's executive council. They claimed that since Muslims have been in charge for a long time, there was the need for a change. This eventually led to a crisis. Other responses to support witnessing of religious crisis are as follows:

In 2018, a Muslim student was speaking ill of the Christian faith. An attempt to respond by a Christian, led to verbal attacks on both sides. – Student number 278.

In 2018, there was another crisis when the Christian group demanded for a place of worship just as the Muslims on campus. This demand led to crisis on campus 2018 – Student number 83.

In 2020, before the outbreak of the global pandemic, the MSSN committee on campus held a meeting at the faculty of Arts main hall which clashed with another one that was organised by the Christian students' committee. The issue almost degenerated into a crisis, but it was quickly resolved. In order to prevent future occurrences, our Vice-Chancellor has since begun a radical infrastructural development within the campus to give more spaces for various activities on campus. Now we can boast of more than enough classes, auditoriums and faculty buildings – Student number 499.

While some respondents said that the misunderstanding was resolved using dialogue as a tool for peaceful co-existence on campus others believed the situation had not changed.

5. Having friends from people of other faiths

Respondents were asked whether they had friends from adherents of other faiths or not. The result in Figure 5 shows that 97.0% of the respondents indicated that they have friends who do not belong to their faith, while 3.0% do not have such friends. Also, most of the students (56.11 %) indicated that they relate peacefully with people of different faiths to a large extent, 39.89% related peacefully to some extent as revealed in the Figure 6.

6. Religious other as threat to personal security and peaceful co-existence

Respondents were asked about their perception of students from other religions and on whether the latter constitutes a threat to their personal security or not. Their responses as given in Fig 7 shows that 3% considered religious others as threat to their personal security while the majority 97.0% do not consider them as threat to them. Those who considered religious others as threat to them believed extremism exist among people of other religions, based on their different levels of understanding of their faiths. They also noted that some students become violent whenever they noticed any form of conflict in their environment. Some of the respondents also said that some lecturers are guilty of favouritism in terms of the attention they give to students who profess same faiths as theirs, even in grading of examination scripts.

7. Interaction with people of other faiths

The respondents were asked if they usually interact with people of other faiths. Their responses, as shown in Fig 8, shows that most of the students (54.8%) responded that they interact with people of other religion(s), while others (36.45%) responded in the negative, as only they engage and network only with their colleagues who profess faiths other than theirs. Those who professed to relating with people of other faiths believed religion should not be barrier to friendship and good neighbourliness. Some of the sample responses are as follows:

A person is not only known by his/her religious belief or practice, but, also by his/her character. Religion is just a tool towards achieving peace and unity in the society – Student number, 94.

Religion shouldn't be an obstacle to making friends with a fellow student because, both of you can gain from each other academically and through that can achieve peace and harmony – Student number, 168.

We are all human beings created by one God and friendship becomes inevitable when you come across someone your spirit accepts, and the person understands you – Student number, 207.

Just because someone is of a different religion does not mean we cannot share the same thoughts about certain views of life – Student number, 355.

Aside from the fact that the Bible preaches love, one has to make friend with people of different religions in order to foster peace within the society – Student number, 464.

As a good Muslim, I see no harm in associating with people of other religious body. My religion means peace so, I practice peace, love and tolerance – Student number, 489.

8. Consequence of living without peace among people of different faiths

When asked about their thoughts on what could happen if Christian and Muslim students live without love, peace, and harmonious relationship on campus. Responses, as shown in Fig 9, revealed that 28.9% of the

respondents stated that hatred and disunity will increase, 23.5% were of the view that ethnic and religious violence will rise, while 22.5% believed that such a situation can lead to national disintegration. In addition, 15.7% of the respondents opined that there would be an increase in suspicion and distrust, while 8.6% said extremist tendencies would blossom. Other (1.0%) respondents noted that conflicts usually lead to the disruption of learning processes and students become distracted from educational activities.

9. Religious differences and students' behaviour

This section was designed to probe how religious differences of the participants influence their behavioural interactions with their fellow school mates. The result, as shown in Table 2, shows that 76.9% strongly agreed that they live peacefully with their fellow students regardless of religious differences, while 116 (22.1%) agreed to the statement. This suggests that there is tolerance among the students despite their different religious affiliations. When asked if there is unity among those who profess different faiths on campus, 77.7% of the respondents strongly agreed to this, whereas 18.7% of them agreed to this. Also, 68.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that they usually obey their student leaders regardless of their (leader's) religious affiliation, 28.2% agreed also agreed to this.

With reference to the respondents' religious understanding, the majority (73.1%) strongly agreed that they were always careful of utterances that can breed religious violence and intolerance, and 24.0% of them equally agreed to this notion. Moreover, 78.1% of the respondents strongly agreed that reading their religious scripture(s) has helped them in living in peace, unity, and harmony with adherents of other religions; and 19.3% of them also agreed to this.

Table 2: Religious differences and students' behaviours

Opinion statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Regardless of religious differences, I live peacefully with my fellow students	403 (76.9%)	116 (22.1%)	5 (1.0%)	0 (0.0%)
I unite with my colleague whose religion is different from mine because my religion teaches me so	407 (77.7%)	98 (18.7%)	5 (1.0%)	14 (2.7%)
Because of my religious teaching to always obey leaders regardless of religious affiliation, I obey my students' leaders	360 (68.7%)	148 (28.2%)	3 (0.6%)	13 (2.5%)
I am always careful of utterances that may breed religious violence and intolerance because of my religious understanding	383 (73.1%)	126 (24.0%)	5 (1.0%)	10 (1.9%)
The more I read my scripture(s), the better I learn to live in peace, unity and harmony with adherents of other religions	409 (78.1%)	101 (19.3%)	2 (0.40%)	12 (2.3%)

10. Influence of Foreign Ideologies on students' belief system

To know the effects of participant's exposure to foreign ideologies on their beliefs and religious practices, the study probed and obtained opinions, as shown in Table 3.

When asked about whether their exposure to foreign religious thoughts influence their hatred for adherents of other religions, majority (59.0%) of the students strongly disagreed, while 25.8% disagreed. Also, when asked if exposure to foreign religious conflicts could influence violence among students, majority (59.9%) of the students strongly disagreed, while 24.2% disagreed with the statement.

Moreover, 60.9% and 24.4% disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively that exposure to foreign religious conflicts usually influence bad utterances against adherents of other religions. Similarly, most (61.1%) of the respondents reported that they strongly disagreed with the statement that exposure to foreign religious conflicts serves as a motivating factor to fight adherents of other religions, and 24.6% also disagreed with the statement.

Table 3: Influence of Foreign Ideologies on the students' belief system

Opinion statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
My exposure to foreign religious thoughts influences my hatred for adherents of other religions in my university	33 (6.3%)	47 (9.0%)	135 (25.8%)	309 (59.0%)
My exposure to foreign religious conflicts influences my violent behaviour against adherents of other religions in my university	31 (5.9%)	52 (9.9%)	127 (24.2%)	314 (59.9%)
My exposure to foreign religious conflicts influences my bad utterances against adherents of other religions in my university	30 (5.7%)	47 (9.0%)	128 (24.4%)	319 (60.9%)
My exposure to foreign religious conflicts motivates me to fight adherents of other religions in my university	35 (6.7%)	40 (7.6%)	129 (24.6%)	320 (61.1%)

11. Interfaith dialogue

One of the most important aspects of this research is the probe on whether it is desirable or otherwise that interfaith dialogue skills should be taught in educational institutions in Nigeria. The result, as shown in Figure 10 below indicates, that majority of the respondents (82.8%) supported the idea of having interfaith dialogue in Nigerian educational institutions, whereas 17.2% do not see the need for it.

Those who responded in the affirmative argued further that teaching interfaith as a course would ultimately foster national unity among university undergraduates in Nigeria who are considered to be future leaders. The respondents also stated that such a course would create awareness and better understanding of different religions and their worldviews, would bring about peaceful coexistence. Other specific responses are as follows:

A good understanding of other religious worldviews will serve as a catalyst for tolerance and peaceful co-existence – Student number, 24.

In my view, University is a place of rebirth, and if a course in interfaith relations can be introduced, it would go a long way in shaping students' perception about other people's religions – Student number, 145.

If interfaith dialogue and national integration is taught in Nigerian Universities, it will foster better understanding of diversities in Nigeria as a whole– Student number, 343

Most families in Nigeria, do not discuss topics on interfaith relations, therefore, I feel it would be of great importance, if it is catered for in our various campuses across the country. –Student number, 364.

Similarly, when asked whether the introduction of a policy on interfaith dialogue in the NUS can foster national integration and development among undergraduate students, majority (80.92%) of the respondents affirmed the postulation, as given in Figure 11.

Those who affirmed the possibility of using interfaith dialogue for national integration believed it will enlighten those who are unaware of the importance of how interfaith dialogue enhances national integration and development. Other specific responses are reported as follows:

Africans are religious people, if the curriculum is developed along the line of national integration through dialogue skills, it will promote unity and mutual understanding –Student number, 29.

With the growing number of youths in the country, developing a curriculum on national integration will build leadership capacity in them which will invariably translate to national development. – Student number 65.

Understanding is based on knowledge and awareness. Therefore, our unity should not be based on our individual religious beliefs. I also believe that we should purge ourselves of the hatred of others so as to move this country forward. – Student number, 76.

In my view, wherever there is peace and unity, there would be development. Once Christians and Muslims come together to live in peace and unity by respecting their differences, this will foster national integration and development – Student number, 84.

The issues of nation’s development go beyond religious differences, hence, the need for awareness and education of the youths who constitute the majority to work together in trust to foster development in the country– Student number, 391.

There is the need to bring the study of history back into the Nigerian educational curriculum so as to serve as motivating factor to the coming generation and for them to work for peace and national integration – Student number, 371.

Discussion of findings

Most respondents label a crisis as religious only when it involves people of different religious regardless of whether the matter that led to the face-off is rooted in religion or not. This is a serious problem that tend to perpetuate religious crises in a multi-religious society. This, in fact, is a precursor to the perception of the respondents about religious crises in Nigeria. That most respondents have not experienced religious crises at the national or at the campus level suggests that there seem to be relative peace among religious adherents. This position was further corroborated by the finding that most of the respondents have people of other faiths as their friends; and do not consider people of other religion as threat to them.

The perception of most respondents about living in peace with people of other faith was positive, as this would affect their disposition and, in turn, other religious people’s disposition to them as well. This perception will be the basis for religious balance and harmony in the larger (multi-religious) society, which will promote understanding and increase tolerance level to manage the inevitable differences among people of different religions. That most respondents favoured desirability of interfaith dialogue meant the opening of avenue for positive intervention to promote religious harmony among students on the campus. The avenue can always be used to correct wrong impressions and nip likely contentious issues in the bud.

In the Nigerian context where religion has become a ‘victim’ in the hands of its practitioners some of whom invoke the divine as reason for perpetration of violence and for indulgence in acts that run contrary to the normative tenets of both Christianity and Islam. The “voices” that we hear in the above survey are therefore very instructive. Though not that of the perpetrators, the respondents are witnesses and victims of the incidences of ‘religious’ conflicts that the nation has continued to witness since the late 1980s. They represent the genuine concerns that the Nigerian youths have not only for their own future but indeed for that of their country as a

whole. The personal stories shared by the respondents and their individual experiences of interfaith relations on the university of Abuja campus equally furnished insights into how responsive leadership could function not only in mitigating interfaith conflicts but, more importantly, in preventing their occurrence.

In other words, though the respondents identified with different religions and had experienced egregious acts of violence, it was axiomatic that they were all prepared to uphold the principles of peace and harmony that the university cherishes as ideals. Their postures and recommendations, though eclectic and perspectival show that the future holds a great deal of promise for Nigeria as far as peaceful interfaith relations are concerned.

Summary of Findings

The survey has captured the perspectives of undergraduate students in the University of Abuja regarding, the challenges that they face in their daily interactions with their colleagues at the interfaith levels, and second, the inherent implications of the interactions for national integration in Nigeria. In line with the Interpretive Phenomenological Approach (IPA), the respondents constitute a stratified cluster that is homogenous about their age, academic achievements and, the extent to which they have experienced interfaith conflicts across northern parts of Nigeria. It is evident from the survey that most of them have either been victims of or witnesses to interfaith conflicts during the past decade in the country. It is also instructive that for the respondents there have been two “meeting point” in their experience of interfaith relations in the country- a) their places of birth, outside the university of Abuja campus, and b) the university of Abuja campus consequent upon their admission into the undergraduate programme of the university. Whereas the university campus has largely proved to be paradisiacal for interfaith relations, it became evident that majority of the respondents have had to go to great lengths to ensure that the dystopia they experienced in Christian-Muslim relations outside the university campus is not re-enacted on their campus. In other words, for the respondents, the self interfaces with two seemingly contradictory interfaith “others” These are (a) the peaceful religious other on the university campus and, (b) the religious other outside the campus whose view of adherents of faiths apart from theirs is that of a competitor, the adversary, and the implacable enemy.

There is no ambiguity whatsoever that all the respondents’ desire a peaceful interfaith university campus. This became clear from the consensus that the introduction of courses on interfaith dialogue into existing curriculum of undergraduate programmes of higher institutions of learning in Nigeria is a desideratum. They contended that such a course would incentivize peaceful co-existence among students on campus and ultimately impact the larger Nigerian society. It is also evident from the survey that the religious crises that Nigeria has experienced in parts of the country were partly caused by lack of adequate knowledge and understanding of the worldviews of adherents of other faiths. In other words, students on the University of Abuja campus recognized that despite their identification with different faiths and beliefs, they were all future partakers and stakeholders in the future of their country. Knowledge of basic principles of faiths other than one’s own, cultivation of peaceful coexistence, ability to establish friendship across religious divides, and the avoidance of hate speech were identified as critical factors that would enhance interfaith relations on the university.

Conclusion

Peaceful interfaith relations on Nigeria University campuses are a desideratum and a catalyst for national integration. However, it is clear from the findings of this paper that both Christian and Muslim students on the university of Abuja campus acknowledged the lack of tolerance and deep understanding of the fundamental tenets of both Christianity and Islam by their adherents as factors for the incessant violence that Nigeria has witnessed in the northern parts of the country. This paper has also shown that conscious emplacement of instruments that could promote harmonious interfaith relations among undergraduate students in the NUS such as curriculum on interfaith dialogue and policy document that would guide and regulate religious activities on university campuses are both urgent and important. Until and unless the afore-mentioned recommendations are put in place, the search for national integration by Nigeria would continue to be a mirage.

Recommendations

To improve on the modest achievements recorded so far by the authorities of the University of Abuja in the area of interfaith relations, at least two critical elements should be given utmost priority. These include the formulation of robust policy for intra- and interfaith activities on the campus and the introduction of interfaith dialogue as a course especially at the undergraduate level. This, it is envisioned, would promote interfaith harmony, incentivize pluralism and strengthen the nation's diversity. Government agencies that were established to promote unity and diversity such as National Orientation Agency (NOA) also need to do more in order that they may deliver on their mandates. One other critical factor that can promote peaceful interfaith relations and ultimately national integration is for religious leaders to consider the pulpit (Mimbar) as sacred spaces where love, compassion and preservation of human life would be core values. They should also exemplify the correct messages of both the Bible and the Quran in their conduct. It is equally expedient that University administrators and faculties purge themselves of religious sentiments and bigotry. Equally important is for adherents of various religions and beliefs on university campuses to cultivate noble attitudes of tolerance and accommodation of other people's ideologies. Relevant policies that could promote and strengthen peaceful interfaith relations should also be formulated by both the National Universities Commission (NUC) and the university senate.

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